

LAMPIRAN

DATA PENDUKUNG

Berikut ini rancangan program arduino dengan sistem poka yoke pada tugas akhir

```
#include <EEPROM.h>
#include <Wire.h>
#include <LiquidCrystal_I2C.h>
#include <TM1637Display.h>
LiquidCrystal_I2C lcd(0x27 ,16,2); //SCL = A5, SDA = A4

#define CLK 7
#define DIO 6
TM1637Display display(CLK, DIO);

const int sinput = 5;
const int buzzer = 13;
const int tombolup = 10;
const int tomboldown = 9;
const int tombolenter = 8;
const int cutoffscrewdriver = 12;
const int sensorpokayoke = 11;
const int solenoid = 3;

int relay2 = 0; //Pokayoke
int relay = 0;
int relaywaktu = 0;
int statetombolup = 0;
int statetomboldown = 0;
int setnilai = 0;
int counter = 1; //
int counter2 = 0;
```

```
int sensor = 0;
int slidinglocktimer = 0;

int counting; //v1.12
int totSet; //v1.12

boolean stopdong = false;
boolean stopit = false;
boolean stopreset = false;
boolean stopreverse = true;
boolean timerslanting = true; // biarin aja
int count = 0;
int count1 = 0;
int i;
int i1;
int variabletimer = 1;
int variabletimer2 = 2;

boolean torquelock = false; //v1.20

#define TEST_DELAY 2000
const uint8_t SEG_Zonk[] = {
    SEG_G,      // Z
    SEG_G,      // o
    SEG_G,      // n
    SEG_G,      // k
};

const uint8_t SEG_DONE[] = {
    SEG_B | SEG_C | SEG_D | SEG_E | SEG_G,      // d
    SEG_A | SEG_B | SEG_C | SEG_D | SEG_E | SEG_F, // O
    SEG_C | SEG_E | SEG_G,                      // n
    SEG_A | SEG_D | SEG_E | SEG_F | SEG_G      // E
};
```

```

const uint8_t SEG_Error[] = {
  SEG_A | SEG_D | SEG_E | SEG_G | SEG_F,    // E
  SEG_G | SEG_E,                            // r
  SEG_C | SEG_D | SEG_E | SEG_G,          // o
  SEG_G | SEG_E,                            // r
};

const uint8_t SEG_Hios[] = {
  SEG_F | SEG_E | SEG_G | SEG_B | SEG_C,    // H
  SEG_B | SEG_C,                            // I
  SEG_A | SEG_B | SEG_C | SEG_D | SEG_E | SEG_F, // O
  SEG_A | SEG_F | SEG_G | SEG_C | SEG_D,    // S
};

void setup()
{
  display.setBrightness(7); //maximum brightness

  // put your setup code here, to run once:
  pinMode(sdinput, INPUT); // ok
  pinMode(buzzer, OUTPUT); // ok
  pinMode(tombolup, INPUT);
  pinMode(tomboldown, INPUT);
  pinMode(tombolenter, INPUT);
  pinMode(sensorpokayoke, INPUT);
  pinMode(cutoffscrewdriver, OUTPUT); // ok
  pinMode(solenoid, OUTPUT); // solenoid
  pinMode(4, INPUT); //realy waktu ok (awalnya A4)

  lcd.backlight();
  lcd.begin();

  Serial.begin(9600);

```

```

digitalWrite(buzzer, LOW);
lcd.setCursor(0,0);
lcd.print(" SCREW COUNTER ");
lcd.setCursor(0,1);
lcd.print("  Ver 1.30  ");
//v1.01 : change timer from 3 to 2
//v1.11 : remove selecting screw
//v1.12 : add more duration when screw finished from 20 to 50
//v1.13 : while sensor get, screwdriver ignore sensor condition
//v1.20 : prevent double counting
//v1.21 : add tot screw and tot set
//v1.30 : improve minor bug, and add bug for repair later
display.setSegments(SEG_Hios);
delay(1000);
lcd.setCursor(0,0);
lcd.print("          ");
lcd.setCursor(1,0);
lcd.print("          ");
}

void loop() {

counting = EEPROM.read(0); //v1.21
totSet = EEPROM.read(1); //v1.21

//CHOOSING SCREW TYPE
teacing:

while(1){
  digitalWrite(buzzer, LOW); // matiin buzzer

  statetombolup = digitalRead(tombolup) ;
  statetomboldown = digitalRead(tomboldown);

```

```
setnilai = digitalRead(tombolenter);
relay = digitalRead(sdinput);
relaywaktu = digitalRead(4);
/*
lcd.setCursor(0,0);
lcd.print("Pilih Screw ");

if(variabletimer == 1){
  lcd.setCursor(0,1);
  lcd.print("LV45701-002A");
}
if(statetombolup == LOW){
  Serial.println("teaching");
  delay(150);
  if(variabletimer >= 7){
    variabletimer = 0;
  }
  variabletimer++;
  if(variabletimer == 1){
    lcd.setCursor(0,1);
    lcd.print("LV45701-002A");
  }
  if(variabletimer == 2){
    lcd.setCursor(0,1);
    lcd.print("LV45701-003A");
  }
  if(variabletimer == 3){
    lcd.setCursor(0,1);
    lcd.print("QYSDST2606ZA");
  }
  if(variabletimer == 4){
    lcd.setCursor(0,1);
    lcd.print("QYSDSF2006ZA");
  }
}
```

```
if(variabletimer == 5){
  lcd.setCursor(0,1);
  lcd.print("QYSPSF2006ZA");
}
if(variabletimer == 6){
  lcd.setCursor(0,1);
  lcd.print("QYSDSF2008ZA");
}
if(variabletimer == 7){
  lcd.setCursor(0,1);
  lcd.print("QYSPSF2008ZA");
}
Serial.println(variabletimer);
delay(150);
}

if(statetomboldown == LOW){
  Serial.println("teaching");
  delay(150);
  if(variabletimer <= 1){
    variabletimer = 8;
  }
  variabletimer--;
  if(variabletimer == 1){
    lcd.setCursor(0,1);
    lcd.print("LV45701-002A");
  }
  if(variabletimer == 2){
    lcd.setCursor(0,1);
    lcd.print("LV45701-003A");
  }
  if(variabletimer == 3){
    lcd.setCursor(0,1);
    lcd.print("QYSDST2606ZA");
```

```
    }  
    if(variabletimer == 4){  
        lcd.setCursor(0,1);  
        lcd.print("QYSDSF2006ZA");  
    }  
    if(variabletimer == 5){  
        lcd.setCursor(0,1);  
        lcd.print("QYSPSF2006ZA");  
    }  
    if(variabletimer == 6){  
        lcd.setCursor(0,1);  
        lcd.print("QYSDSF2008ZA");  
    }  
    if(variabletimer == 7){  
        lcd.setCursor(0,1);  
        lcd.print("QYSPSF2008ZA");  
    }  
    delay(50);  
    Serial.println(variabletimer);  
    delay(150);  
}  
  
if (setnilai == LOW){  
    Serial.println("timer save");  
    digitalWrite(buzzer, HIGH);  
    delay(100);  
    lcd.setCursor(0,0);  
    lcd.print ("   CONFIRMED   ");  
    digitalWrite(buzzer, LOW);  
    delay(800);  
  
    lcd.setCursor(0,0);  
    lcd.print("Jumlah Screw:   ");  
    variabletimer2 = variabletimer;
```

```
Serial.println(variabletimer2);
delay(200);

if(variabletimer == 1){
  variabletimer2 = 2; //1.01
  Serial.print("USE LV45701-002A");
}
if(variabletimer == 2){
  variabletimer2 = 2; //1.01
  Serial.print("USE LV45701-003A");
}
if(variabletimer == 3){
  variabletimer2 = 2; //1.01
  Serial.print("QYSDST2606ZA = 3");
}
if(variabletimer == 4){
  variabletimer2 = 2; //1.01
  Serial.print("QYSDSF2006ZA = 3");
}
if(variabletimer == 5){
  variabletimer2 = 2; //1.01
  Serial.print("QYSPSF2006ZA = 3");
}
if(variabletimer == 6){
  variabletimer2 = 2; //1.01
  Serial.print("QYSDSF2008ZA = 3");
}
if(variabletimer == 7){
  variabletimer2 = 2; //1.01
  Serial.print("QYSPSF2008ZA = 3");
}
*/
lcd.setCursor(0,1);
```

```

    lcd.print("      ");
    lcd.setCursor(0,0);
    lcd.print("Jumlah Screw:  ");
    lcd.setCursor(0,1);
    lcd.print("Max = 19      ");
    digitalWrite(buzzer, LOW);
    goto jalan;
  //}
}

//CHOOSING QTY OF SCREW
jalan:
while(1)
{

    statetombolup = digitalRead(tombolup);
    statetomboldown = digitalRead(tomboldown);
    setnilai = digitalRead(tombolenter);
    relay = digitalRead(sdinput);
    relaywaktu = digitalRead(4);

    if(counter == 1){
        lcd.setCursor(0,0);
        lcd.print("Jumlah Screw:  ");
        lcd.setCursor(14,0);
        lcd.print(counter);
        display.showNumberDec(counter);
    }

    if(statetombolup == LOW){
        Serial.println("jalan");
        delay(150);
        if(counter >= 19){
            counter = 0;

```

```
}  
counter++;  
lcd.setCursor(0,0);  
lcd.print("Jumlah Screw:  ");  
lcd.setCursor(14,0);  
lcd.print(counter); //Display QTY of Screw  
Serial.println(counter);  
display.showNumberDec(counter);  
delay(150);  
}  
  
if(statetomboldown == LOW){  
  Serial.println("jalan");  
  delay(150);  
  if(counter <= 1){  
    counter = 20;  
  }  
  counter--;  
  Serial.println(counter);  
  lcd.setCursor(0,0);  
  lcd.print("Jumlah Screw:  ");  
  lcd.setCursor(14,0);  
  lcd.print(counter); //TAMPILKAN QTY SCREW  
  display.showNumberDec(counter);  
  delay(150);  
}  
  
if(setnilai == LOW){  
  counter2 = counter;  
  Serial.println("ok");  
  digitalWrite(buzzer, HIGH);  
  delay(200);  
  
  lcd.setCursor(0,0);
```

```
lcd.print("  CONFIRMED  ");
lcd.setCursor(0,1);
lcd.print("          ");
delay(300);
digitalWrite(buzzer, LOW);
delay(200);
/*
if(variabletimer == 1){
  variabletimer2 = 2; //1.01
  Serial.print("USE LV45701-002A");
}
if(variabletimer == 2){
  variabletimer2 = 2; //1.01
  Serial.print("USE LV45701-003A");
}
if(variabletimer == 3){
  variabletimer2 = 2; //1.01
  Serial.print("QYSDST2606ZA = 14");
}
if(variabletimer == 4){
  variabletimer2 = 2; //1.01
  Serial.print("QYSDSF2006ZA = 5");
}
if(variabletimer == 5){
  variabletimer2 = 2; //1.01
  Serial.print("QYSPSF2006ZA = 5");
}
if(variabletimer == 6){
  variabletimer2 = 2; //1.01
  Serial.print("QYSDSF2008ZA = 6");
}
if(variabletimer == 7){
  variabletimer2 = 2; //1.01
  Serial.print("QYSPSF2008ZA = 9");
```

```
}
*/
lcd.clear();
Serial.print("sisa screw : ");
Serial.println(counter2);
display.showNumberDec(counter2);
delay(200);
goto jalan1;
}
}

//STARTING PROCESS
jalan1:

counting = EEPROM.read(0); //v1.21
totSet = EEPROM.read(1); //v1.21

while(1)
{
    setnilai = digitalRead(tombolenter);
    relay = digitalRead(sdinput);
    relaywaktu = digitalRead(4);

    lcd.setCursor(9,0);
    lcd.print("TIME:");
    lcd.setCursor(9,1);
    lcd.print("QTY :");
    lcd.setCursor(14,1);
    lcd.print(counter2);
    lcd.setCursor(0,0); //v1.21
    lcd.print("TScw:"); //v1.21
    lcd.setCursor(5,0); //v1.21
    lcd.print(counting); //v1.21
    lcd.setCursor(0,1); //v1.21
```

```
lcd.print("TSet:"); //v1.21
lcd.setCursor(5,1); //v1.21
lcd.print(totSet); //v1.21
display.showNumberDec(counter2);
/*
if(variabletimer == 1){
    lcd.setCursor(0,1);
    lcd.print("LV45701-002A");
}
if(variabletimer == 2){
    lcd.setCursor(0,1);
    lcd.print("LV45701-003A");
}
if(variabletimer == 3){
    lcd.setCursor(0,1);
    lcd.print("QYSDST2606ZA");
}
if(variabletimer == 4){
    lcd.setCursor(0,1);
    lcd.print("QYSDSF2006ZA");
}
if(variabletimer == 5){
    lcd.setCursor(0,1);
    lcd.print("QYSPSF2006ZA");
}
if(variabletimer == 6){
    lcd.setCursor(0,1);
    lcd.print("QYSDSF2008ZA");
}
if(variabletimer == 7){
    lcd.setCursor(0,1);
    lcd.print("QYSPSF2008ZA");
}
}
```

```
/*if(setnilai == LOW){ //hapus program ini kalo mau gk bisa di reset
  counter2 = counter;
  Serial.println("ok");
  digitalWrite(buzzer, HIGH);
  delay(200);
  lcd.setCursor(0,0);
  lcd.print("  CONFIRMED  ");
  delay(300);
  digitalWrite(buzzer, LOW);
  delay(200);

  if(variabletimer == 1){
    variabletimer2 = 3;
    Serial.print("USE LV45701-002A");
  }
  if(variabletimer == 2){
    variabletimer2 = 3;
    Serial.print("USE LV45701-003A");
  }
  if(variabletimer == 3){
    variabletimer2 = 3;
    Serial.print("QYSDST2606ZA = 14");
  }
  if(variabletimer == 4){
    variabletimer2 = 3;
    Serial.print("QYSDSF2006ZA = 5");
  }
  if(variabletimer == 5){
    variabletimer2 = 3;
    Serial.print("QYSPSF2006ZA = 5");
  }
  if(variabletimer == 6){
    variabletimer2 = 3;
    Serial.print("QYSDSF2008ZA = 6");
  }
}
```

```

}
if(variabletimer == 7){
    variabletimer2 = 3;
    Serial.print("QYSPSF2008ZA = 9");
}
lcd.setCursor(0,0);
lcd.print("Time:");
lcd.setCursor(9,0);
lcd.print("QTY:");
lcd.setCursor(13,0);
lcd.print(counter2);e
lcd.setCursor(14,1);
lcd.print(variabletimer2); //timer yg di setting

Serial.print("sisa screw : ");
Serial.println(counter2);
display.showNumberDec(counter2);
delay(200);
}*/

if((counter2 == counter) && (digitalRead(sensorpokayoke) == LOW )){ // low
    berarti ada panel
    digitalWrite(cutoffscrewdriver, HIGH);
    digitalWrite(solenoid, HIGH);
    //lcd.setCursor(15,0);
    //lcd.print("*");
}
/*if((counter2 == counter) && (digitalRead(sensorpokayoke) == HIGH )){ // low
    berarti ada panel
    digitalWrite(cutoffscrewdriver, LOW); //low berarti screw driver mati
    lcd.setCursor(15,0);
    lcd.print(" ");
}*/
if(relaywaktu == LOW){

```

```
count++;
delay(10); // 0.1 detik di hp
i = count;
Serial.println(i);
lcd.setCursor(9,0);
lcd.print("TIME: ");
lcd.setCursor(14,0);
lcd.print(i);
}
if(count>1){
  torquelock = true;
}
if(relay == LOW && torquelock == true && stopit == false && i >=
  variabeltimer2){ //screw pendek minimal 18 ms
  stopreverse = false;
  counter2--;
  torquelock = false;
  digitalWrite(buzzer, HIGH);
  delay(100);
  digitalWrite(buzzer, LOW);
  timerslanting = true;

  Serial.print("sisa screw : ");
  Serial.println(counter2);
  display.showNumberDec(counter2);
  lcd.setCursor(9,1);
  lcd.print("QTY : ");
  lcd.setCursor(14,1);
  lcd.print(counter2);
  stopit = true;
  counting++;
  EEPROM.write(0, counting);
  delay(300);
```

```
if(counter2 <= 0){
  display.showNumberDec(counter2);
  Serial.print("sisa screw : ");
  Serial.println(counter2);
  digitalWrite(cutoffscrewdriver, LOW); //mati
  digitalWrite(solenoid, LOW);
  totSet++;
  EEPROM.write(1, totSet);
  display.setSegments(SEG_DONE);
  digitalWrite(solenoid, LOW);

  digitalWrite(buzzer, HIGH);
  delay(100);
  digitalWrite(buzzer, LOW);
  delay(100);
  digitalWrite(buzzer, HIGH);
  delay(1000);
  digitalWrite(buzzer, LOW);
  goto solenoid;
  //counter2 = counter;
}
Serial.print("sisa screw : ");
Serial.println(counter2);
display.showNumberDec(counter2);
lcd.setCursor(9,1);
lcd.print("QTY : ");
lcd.setCursor(14,1);
lcd.print(counter2);
stopit = true;
delay (300);
}
if(stopit == false && i < variabeltimer2){
  timerslanting = false;
}
```

```
if(relay == HIGH){
  stopit = false;
}
if(relaywaktu == HIGH){
  delay(25);
  torquelock = false;
  count = 0;
}
if(setnilai == HIGH){
  count1 = 0;
}
if(setnilai == LOW){
  count1++;
  delay(10); // 0.1 detik di hp
  i1 = count1;
  if(i1>20){
    counting = 0;
    totSet = 0;
    EEPROM.write(0, counting);
    EEPROM.write(1, totSet);
    lcd.clear();
  }
}
}

//Solenoid
solenoid:
slidinglocktimer = 0;
while(1){
  lcd.setCursor(0,0);
  lcd.print("  DONE  ");
  lcd.setCursor(0,1);
  lcd.print("      ");
  if(slidinglocktimer < 50){
```

```
display.showNumberDec(slidinglocktimer);
slidinglocktimer++;
if(slidinglocktimer == 50){
    display.setSegments(SEG_DONE);
}
}
if((digitalRead(sensorpokayoke) == HIGH) && slidinglocktimer == 50){
    lcd.setCursor(0,0);
    lcd.print("      ");
    lcd.setCursor(0,1);
    lcd.print("      ");
    slidinglocktimer = 0;
    counter2 = counter;
    goto jalan1;
}
}
}
```